

ORGANIZING EXPERIMENTAL WORK FOR IMPROVING THE PROCESS OF MANAGING EDUCATION QUALITY IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17808743>

Abstract. *This article covers the conditions for organizing experimental research during scientific work. During the experiment, the issues of respondents' ability to apply digital technologies in management activities based on the results of training in management courses were analyzed. The importance of using digital technologies to improve the quality of education in school management was noted based on the final results.*

Keywords: *education quality, management, education quality assessment, respondent, digital education.*

Introduction

Improving the Quality of Education in General Secondary Schools requires effective organization of the teaching process, evaluation of teachers' performance, monitoring student outcomes, and continuous development. Increasing education quality is carried out within the framework of state policy, and specific mechanisms have been introduced for the implementation of this process. Accordingly, the management of education quality in general secondary schools is carried out based on regulatory frameworks. This process in the Republic of Uzbekistan is implemented on the basis of the Law "On Education" and the relevant Decree relating to the school system. According to Resolution N. 91, dated February 14, 2024 the Ministry of Preschool and School Education introduced a system of education quality monitoring based on risk assessment in state general secondary education institutions.

Education quality monitoring is conducted in state secondary schools based on the analysis of the teaching process and organizational results of education. Initially, the monitoring is carried out by the internal monitoring department of the institution, and the collected results are submitted to the Ministry of Preschool and School Education via an electronic platform for education quality monitoring. Through this system, the mechanisms for evaluating and controlling education quality in schools are improved. This process highlights the implementation of modern assessment methods, analysis of student outcomes, evaluation of teacher performance, and cooperation with parents. Risk-based monitoring aims to detect potential issues in advance. Among the key factors for improving education quality in general secondary schools are professional development of teachers, updating educational curricula, and organizing parent meetings.

Based on the current situation, the creation of a high-quality education structure, ensuring continuous education, and introducing effective mechanisms for managing the public education system remain pressing tasks in the process of reforming the general education system. Model curricula have been developed for general secondary school teachers to ensure quality in school education. Establishing an effective timetable, introducing an assessment system within schools, and strengthening the role of teacher competency are crucial for improving quality. Effective quality management in education requires continuous monitoring of the teaching process, as well

as strengthening cooperation with teachers and parents. Based on the research focus, the use of digital educational technologies in quality management of school education enables electronic monitoring of the learning process, electronic tracking of teachers' research activity, and documentation of educational activities. This process requires efficient time management and responsible engagement with the learning process. During the research, the digital competency of school principals in managing school administration through digital technologies was studied.

Digital technologies enable the preparation of engaging learning materials, provide opportunities for distance learning, and support individualized education, all of which contribute to improving education quality. Through the digitization of the school learning process, digital education increases students' independent learning skills, allows teachers to efficiently manage educational curricula, and helps analyze learning outcomes in real time. As a result of the experimental work aimed at improving the quality of education through digital technologies, respondents were evaluated using criteria related to information selection, data processing, analysis of evidence, and information management, based on information and media literacy standards. The selection of these criteria makes it possible to assess the extent to which digital technologies are being applied in schools.

However, there are some existing challenges in this process, such as insufficient internet access, low levels of digital literacy, and inadequate data security. The integration of digital technologies in schools is one of the main factors contributing to improving education quality, modernizing the learning process, and enhancing teacher qualifications. Creating a digital learning environment also helps meet the individual needs of students. Within the framework of the current project "Use of ICT and digital education", support is being provided for digital transformation in education. Collaboration has been established with teachers and education leaders to implement digital education programs, introduce AI-based educational tools, and create a sustainable foundation of ICT competencies. As part of this project, it is planned to equip teachers with digital tools, as this is essential for improving educational practices.

In the course of our research, we analyzed the digital competency of respondents who completed managerial training courses in 2024 and 2025. The digital competency of participants from the 2024 management training courses was also assessed. Analysis of school principals' use of digital technologies across the Republic shows that principals from Samarkand, Namangan, Andijan, Khorezm, and Tashkent regions demonstrate higher digital competence compared to other regions. According to assessment results, school principals from Syrdarya, Navoi, Surkhandarya regions and Tashkent city showed lower levels of digital literacy. During the experimental phase, the level of digital technology proficiency among principals participating in 2025 management training course was also identified. For this stage, participants of the Management Course organized at the A. Avloni National Institute of Pedagogical Mastery were selected. Analyses were conducted on participants enrolled in the professional development programs from May to June 2025. The results showed that school principals from Surkhandarya and Tashkent regions demonstrated higher levels of digital competency in the final testing stage.

The duration of the experimental study covers two years. In 2024, a total of 145 school principals participated in managerial professional development courses. Of these, 72 principals were part of the control group, with 35 participants receiving certificates. Meanwhile, 73 school principals were included in the experimental group, and 40 of them obtained certificates after completing the course. In 2025, a total of 147 school principals took part in the managerial training courses, with 73 principals in the control group and 74 principals in the experimental group. At

the beginning of the experiment, a questionnaire was administered to assess the existing level of school principals' digital competence.

Name of the direction and period of the experiment	Number of participants in the experiment n_i	Performance indicators	
		Passed	Not passed
2024 Management training course Participants (145 School Principals)	Control Group: $n_2 = 72$ participants	35 participants 48,6 %	37 participants 51,4%
	Experimental Group: $n_1 = 73$ participants	40 participants 54,8%	33 participants 45,2 %
2025 Management training course Participants (146 School Principals)	Control Group: $n_2 = 72$ participants	43 participants 59,7%	29 participants 40,3%
	Experimental Group: $n_1 = 74$ participants	62 participants 83,8%	12 participants 16,2%

Based on the survey results, gaps were identified, and competency assessment criteria were determined. These criteria included: information selection, data processing, analysis of evidence, information management, and information and media literacy. Based on the obtained results, it was observed that the “teaching effectiveness assessment” criterion was higher than 1, while the “cognitive level assessment” criterion showed values greater than 0. This indicates that the level of academic achievement in the experimental group was higher than that of the control group. Thus, statistical analysis confirmed that the experimental tests conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of school principals' acquisition of digital competencies were efficient. According to the analysis, if we compare the knowledge levels of principals who participated in managerial training courses in 2024 and 2025—specifically, those who passed and failed the final assessment—we obtain the following calculations.

Based on the results of the experimental study, we analyzed the effectiveness of school principals' acquisition of digital competencies using Student's mathematical-statistical method to compare the average learning outcomes of the experimental and control groups. In the experimental study, 145 school principals participated in 2024, of whom 73 were assigned to the experimental group and 72 to the control group. In 2025, 146 school principals took part, with 74 in the experimental group and 72 in the control group. According to the obtained results, mathematical statistical indicators were calculated for the final stage of the experiment. These included average quadratic deviation, sample variance, coefficient of variation, Student's t-test value, degrees of freedom, and confidence intervals. These results are presented in the following table.

In the table: Column 2 presents data on information selection at the beginning of the experiment, Column 3 presents information selection at the end of the experiment, Column 4 shows data processing at the beginning, Column 5 shows data processing at the end, Column 6 presents evidence analysis at the beginning, Column 7 presents evidence analysis at the end, Column 8 provides information management at the beginning, Column 9 provides information management at the end, Column 10 shows information and media literacy at the beginning, Column 11 shows information and media literacy at the end of the experiment. These results are reflected in the table below.

Thus, during the pedagogical experiment, it was identified that the effectiveness of school principals' acquisition of digital competencies in the experimental group exceeded that of the control group. The average performance of the experimental group was higher by:

13 points in information selection, 12.6 points in data processing, 12.3 points in evidence analysis, 14.3 points in information management, and 13.3 points in information and media literacy.

Table-2

\bar{X}	\bar{Y}	S_x^2	S_y^2	C_x	C_y	$T_{x,y}$	K	Δ_x	Δ_y
1,82	1,86	At the beginning of the experiment, no effectiveness was achieved.							
2,36	1,97	0,5704	0,6291	4	5	3,05	146,74	0,17	0,18
1,94	1,91	At the beginning of the experiment, no effectiveness was achieved.							
2,41	2,03	0,5619	0,6291	4	5	2,99	142,08	0,17	0,18
1,91	1,92	At the beginning of the experiment, no effectiveness was achieved.							
2,38	2,01	0,5756	0,6299	4	5	2,89	146,74	0,17	0,18
1,79	1,78	At the beginning of the experiment, no effectiveness was achieved.							
2,44	2,01	0,5464	0,7099	4	5	3,28	140,78	0,17	0,19
2,02	1,91	At the beginning of the experiment, no effectiveness was achieved.							
2,43	2,03	0,5451	0,7091	4	5	3,05	140,78	0,17	0,19

In conclusion, the obtained results show that the teaching effectiveness assessment indicator is greater than 1, and the cognitive level assessment indicator is greater than 0. This confirms that the learning performance of the experimental group was higher than that of the control group. Therefore, the statistical analysis clearly demonstrates the effectiveness of the experimental tests conducted to measure school principals' acquisition of digital competencies.

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